

Dear colleagues,

Scenarios play a critical role in IPCC Assessment Reports for projected global, regional, and national futures, integrating information across Earth system responses, alongside climate mitigation, adaptation, and socioeconomic development.

We, as a group of IPCC AR7 authors, recall the recommendations from the [Report](#) of the IPCC Workshop on the Use of Scenarios in the Sixth Assessment Report and Subsequent Assessments in April 2023 in Bangkok. We are engaged to facilitate a rigorous, comprehensive, and cross-disciplinary assessment, with a full commitment to diversity and inclusivity, to support coordination across WGI, WGII, WGIII, and the SR Cities reports on the use and assessment of models and scenarios in this assessment cycle.

As previously communicated in the [IPCC's letter to the National Focal Points](#), there will be no single IPCC-endorsed "scenarios database" to support the Seventh Assessment. The IPCC AR7 will strive to consider all relevant scenarios, pathways, and futures data on physical climate science, impacts and adaptation, and mitigation for the IPCC assessment. This goal will be greatly facilitated if scenarios are made publicly available in common formats to enable comparability and transparent analysis. With this letter, we seek your support in this endeavor and:

- Invite all researchers to archive the underlying information on scenarios, pathways, and futures from any peer-reviewed publications, especially published post AR6 (after 2021), in a spreadsheet-compatible, readable/interoperable format that enables assessment (e.g., in online supplementary material or data repositories, with metadata and units clearly specified, following FAIR principles for data reusability).
- Recognize the essential role of community databases in fostering inclusivity, establishing the necessary formatting consistency across different purposes, and enabling the scientific communities to conduct peer-reviewed research and hence make the data more accessible to scenario user groups, such as the IPCC authors (as well as the wider community), for a timely assessment. Therefore, we invite all researchers to submit scenarios to the community scenario databases:
 - For global and national/regional emissions scenarios, see more detailed information [here](#). Relevant community databases have been developed for different purposes. These include the [Scenario Compass Initiative](#) for global emissions scenarios, the [IAMC Scientific Working Group on National Scenarios](#) for regional and national emissions scenarios, and model intercomparison projects open for scenario data submission in CMIP7 (e.g., Policy-aligned Model Intercomparison Project, PoMIP), which will later publish corresponding gridded climate projections from complex Earth System models at CMIP7-ESGF. We stress that we are committed to assessing a broad and diverse set of relevant accessible scenarios, not just those submitted to the community databases.
 - Information on community databases for other purposes, such as sectoral scenarios (e.g., transport, industry, buildings, or power sector), impacts, adaptation, and sustainable development, will be provided when available.

Initial submissions are sought as soon as they are available, while further submissions will be considered before the literature cut-off dates (in the second half of 2027, taking into account the staggered timelines of the three Reports), which will be specified at a later stage.

If you would like to highlight any important information on other scenario resources, including peer-reviewed publications, project- or publication-related scenario data, or grey literature that should be considered, please fill in the survey form [here](#). Please note that while submission will enable and support consideration by authors, it does not guarantee that any particular scenario will be explicitly included in the assessment or highlighted in any specific figure or table.

Any further suggestions are welcome via the survey form or directly contact: Da Zhang (Tsinghua University), Evelina Trutnevyte (University of Geneva), or Chris Smith (IIASA).

We appreciate your support and welcome you to circulate this letter in your communities.

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